

1 **Simultaneously observing particle and wave behavior of light**

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Abstract

Utilizing methods first theorized by T. Young to test whether light mimicked the behavior of classical waves, we demonstrated interference patterns indicating wave behavior with single photons. Our methods involved measuring the horizontal location of individual photons on the surface of a detector after a light beam passed through a double-slit blocker. The two slits produced an interference pattern which demonstrates the perplexing quantum phenomena of photons interfering with themselves– a fundamental deviation from classical physics.

7 I. INTRODUCTION

8 One of the foundational questions within the field of quantum mechanics was whether
9 light behaved with as a classical particle or as a wave. In his famous Double-Slit experiment,
10 Thomas Young sought to prove that light behaves like a classical wave by observing an
11 interference pattern when a light beam passed through two parallel vertical slits[1]. He
12 expected that, if light acted in the same manner a wave, the interference pattern– bands
13 of very bright and very dark measurements caused by the light waves interacting with
14 one another– would appear upon downstream measurements of the slits. However if light
15 was instead made up of very small particles, one very bright spot directly in the center
16 of the measurement area that faded slowly off to the sides would arise where the particles
17 scattered and landed. After performing his Double-Slit experiment, Thomas Young observed
18 an interference pattern, indicating that light has wave-like properties.

19 FIG. 1. An 1807 drawing by Young illustrating the principles of the double-slit experiment.
20

FIG. 2. A photo of the interference pattern produced by a laser in a modern two-slit experimental apparatus.

21 Puzzlingly, later experiments were able to detect individual packets of light – photons–
22 which behaved as particles upon detection, but still built up an interference pattern [2]. An
23 object exhibiting properties of both particles and waves had never been observed before,
24 and could not exist in the realm of classical mechanics. This deviation from classical physics

25 is what Feynman referred to as the heart of quantum mechanics in his 1963 lectures. This
26 phenomenon is commonly referred to as wave-particle duality of light, although some find
27 that description to be misleading since more advanced understandings of the phenomena
28 deal exclusively with wave functions [3]. Qualitatively, we observe *both* particle and wave
29 qualities in the light downstream of the double slit.

30 **A. Description of Experiment**

31 We utilized the TeachSpin Two-Slit-Apparatus to replicate Young's Two-Slit experiments
32 to measure individual photons and display an interference pattern. The two-slit apparatus
33 sends a light beam along an enclosed U-channel to a photomultiplier. In between the light
34 source and the detector there are a number of components which allowed for adjustment
35 of the slit locations, and thus several different types of measurement. We calibrated these
36 components to ensure that the light beam was centered against the photomultiplier. The
37 final mounted slit that the light beam encounters is a single slit directly in front of the
38 detector, and is adjusted by means of a micrometer. The detector slit allows only a slim
39 vertical stream of light to reach the photomultiplier. This allowed us to measure the exact
40 location along the surface of the detector where photons were detected. The data output
41 from the photomultiplier is a voltage which could be read by a counter/timer and digital
42 oscilloscope, allowing us to make a count of how many photons reached a given point on the
43 detector.

44 In order to count as many photons as possible without counting background noise, we
45 adjusted the trigger level on both the counter/timer and oscilloscope so that they were
46 identical and provided the greatest difference between dark and bright counts upon repeated
47 measurement. Further discussion of our comparison between bright and dark counts is
48 relegated to the data subsection of the results section.

49 **II. RESULTS**

50 **A. Taking Data**

51 Our data consists of measurements of the counts read from the photomultiplier over an
52 interval of 10 seconds. Each count was triggered by the arrival of a photon at the detector.

53 The detector then sends a voltage signal as an output from the TeachSpin Apparatus that is
54 then read by a counter/timer. The counter/timer counts the number of times the TeachSpin
55 Apparatus measured the arrival of a photon. Bright counts were measured with the bulb's
56 light on and with the detector's shutter open. To account for the noise that we would
57 measure, Dark counts were also measured. Dark counts were measured with the shutter
58 closed.

59 B. The Data

FIG. 3. Raw data from slit with $d = 14$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

60 Qualitatively, this data in Figure 3 and Figure 4 absolutely supports the wave-particle
61 understanding of the behavior of light. Although only one photon reached the detector at a
62 time, we still observed positive and negative interference when the double slit was in place.
63 Note also that the dark counts are well below the total counts, indicating that the majority
64 of the particles we measured were photons. This can be compared to the single slit, Figure
65 5, which displays no interference pattern.

FIG. 4. Raw data from slit with $d = 18$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

FIG. 5. Raw data from the single slit imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

66 **C. Quantified Uncertainty**

67 **III. DATA ANALYSIS**

We utilized the following relation for uncertainty proposed for experiments involving photon counts:

$$\sigma_{r_s}^2 = \sigma_{r_{s+b}}^2 + \sigma_{r_b}^2$$

68 Where r is the count rate, s is the source, b is the background, and, of course, σ is uncertainty.

69 We made the following determinations:

70 $\sigma_{r_b} = 8.161$, which was the standard deviation of the twelve background counts we
71 measured.

72 $\sigma_{r_{b+s}} = 41.296$, which was the standard deviation of twelve different bright counts we
73 performed at the same micrometer location. We selected a micrometer position of 2.5 with
74 the 14 mm slit since this was a location of maximum sensitivity given the steep slope in
75 the graph at this point, demonstrating a dramatic change in photon counts between this
76 micrometer setting and the next.

From this, we calculated the following:

$$\sigma_{r_s} = \sqrt{\sigma_{r_{s+b}}^2 + \sigma_{r_b}^2} = \sqrt{8.161^2 + 41.296^2} = 42.095$$

77 Which we used as error bars on our data. This is significant only when our data neared the
78 dark count values, which is acceptable.

79 **A. Theory**

80 The purpose of this experiment was to test the theory that light behaves with both
81 particle and wave properties. A wave passing through two slits will interfere with itself and
82 produce a pattern of alternating positive and negative interference bands on a detector.
83 Particles passing through two slits will pass through one or the other and produce a peak
84 behind each slit. Therefore, measuring the result of light passing through two slits ought to
85 indicate whether it is a particle or a wave. One of the foundational problems of quantum
86 mechanics is the problem of measurement: by measuring a system, one alters it. Upon
87 measurement of light at very, very low intensities, it is clear that a detector picks up a single
88 point of light— a photon— but that is no proof that light always behaves as a photon particle,
89 since the measurement may have altered its behavior. The demonstration of this is in the
90 single photon double slit experiment we performed. Although only a single photon was in
91 the U-channel at a given time, an interference pattern was produced. This indicates that
92 the light passed through both slits at once, like a wave, but collapsed and hit the detector
93 at exactly one point, like a particle. This is in support of the theory that light demonstrates
94 both wave and particle behaviors.

95 **B. Quantified Analysis**

96 Since the primary purpose of this experiment was to observe a photon interfering with
97 itself, we needed to be reasonably certain that there was only one photon in the U-channel
98 at a time, instead of two photons getting through and interfering with one another. We per-
99 formed the following analysis, and are extremely confident that our data represents photons
100 interfering with themselves.

The probability of a photon being in the U-channel is given by:

$$P(n, \mu) = \frac{(\bar{r} \cdot \Delta t)^n}{n!} \cdot e^{-\bar{r}\Delta t}$$

101 Where:

- 102 • n is the number of events (number of photons reaching the detector)
- 103 • Δt is the amount of time it takes a photon to travel from emission to detector, from
104 the following calculation using L , the length of the U-channel, and c , the speed of
105 light: $= \frac{L}{c} = 1.05m \cdot \frac{1s}{2.9979 \cdot 10^8 m} = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9} s$
- 106 • \bar{r} is the rate of emissions of photons. We estimated this value by taking the maximum
107 emission with a single wide slit in place of the double slits. This ensured that no
108 light was blocked from the detector, and we got a fair estimate. This maximum was
109 $\frac{580 \text{ photons}}{10s} = 58p/s$

110 Using this information, observe the following:

The probability of there being no photons in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$P(0) = e^{-\bar{r}\Delta t} = e^{-58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}} = 0.9999$$

The probability of there being one photon in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$P(1) = (\bar{r}\Delta t) \cdot P(0) = (0.58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9}) \cdot 0.9999 = 2.02 \cdot 10^{-9}$$

The probability of there being two photons in the U-channel in a given Δt is:

$$P(2) = \frac{1}{2}(\bar{r}\Delta t)^2 \cdot P(0) = \frac{1}{2}(0.58 \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{-9})^2 \cdot 0.9999 = 2.06 \cdot 10^{-18}$$

111 Since the probability of there being two photons in the channel at the same time is so
112 much lower (by a factor of 10^{-9}) than the probability of there being one photon in the
113 channel, we can be extremely confident that we are measuring photon self-interference.

We wish to compare our data to the following model:

$$I = I_0 \sin^2(\alpha) \cdot \cos^2(\beta)$$

Where:

$$\sin c(\alpha) = \frac{\sin(\alpha)}{\alpha}$$

$$\beta = \frac{\pi a}{\lambda \sin(\theta)}$$

114 The angle θ is the angle (measured at the double slit in radians) between the midpoint of
115 the U-channel and the point at which the measurement of a photon occurred.

116 Although both data sets clearly display an interference pattern, note that in order to
117 achieve an acceptable fit of the data to the model, we introduced a slight offset in the angle
118 θ of approximately -0.0003 in the $d = 14$, and -0.0012 in the $d = 18$ plots, Figures 7 and
119 8, respectively.

FIG. 6. Curve fit for single slit data imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

FIG. 7. Curve fit for double slit with $d = 14$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

120 **C. Analysis of Curve Fit**

To verify that the data supports the model beyond the visual fit, we utilized a χ^2 test:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{\frac{\text{residuals}^2}{\text{uncertainty}}}{\text{points} - \text{d.o.f.}}$$

121 The residuals were calculated by subtracting a given data point from the value of the
 122 model at that point. The subtraction of the degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) from the number of
 123 data points is standard practice in a χ^2 test.

124 The results of the test were as follows:

125 . $\chi_{14slit}^2 = 0.028$ $\chi_{18slit}^2 = 0.035$ $\chi_{single}^2 = 0.011$.

126 These very low reduced χ^2 values indicate that our data strongly supports the model.

FIG. 8. Curve fit for double slit with $d = 18$ imported directly from the Jupyter notebook.

127 IV. CONCLUSION

128 The data satisfactorily demonstrates photon self-interference, by aligning with the model
 129 of classical interference when only one photon reached the photomultiplier at a time. Ideally,
 130 more data would be taken in the form of both repeated data sets and finer modulation of
 131 the micrometer in the two-slit apparatus to produce more data points in each set, but the
 132 existing data is more than sufficient.

¹³³ [1] T. Young, (1802).

¹³⁴ [2] H. Rauch, Physics World , 15 (2002).

¹³⁵ [3] H. Nikolic, Found Phys **37**, 1563 (2007).